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Digital transformation in agriculture in Russia

KEYWORDS

digital economy,
digitalization of
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the research topic stems from the introduction of digital technologies which enable the optimization of production processes, reduce costs, and improve product quality. Digital solutions contribute to a more rational use of natural resources, reducing the negative impact on the environment and the development of environmentally sustainable agricultural models.

The paper aims to analyze the state of digitalization of agricultural production and to identify reserves for its improvement in Russia.

Materials and methods. The material consisted of research and analytical reports on digital transformation in agriculture, published in scientific journals and reports from international and Russian organizations. The studies were conducted based on data from statistical reports of the Russian Federation, its constituent entities, and the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation over the past decade.

Results. In terms of the use of digital technologies in agricultural production, Russia lags far behind the United States and many European and Asian countries. Along with other factors, and for the same reason, crop yields and the productivity of farm animals in Russia are significantly lower than in these countries. To improve the situation, the Government of the Russian Federation launched two programs: 1) The national project "Digital Economy of the Russian Federation" (in 2018); 2) Digital Agriculture Program (in 2019).

The total budget financing under these two documents for the 7 years (from 2018 to 2024) amounts to 1,934.9 billion rubles. In 2019-2024, 300 billion rubles of this amount will be directed to the Russian agro-industrial complex. Due to such financing, the government intends to achieve an increase in agricultural production of 16.3% by 2025 compared to 2017. Exports of farm products are expected to reach 45 billion dollars. Additionally, investments in the Russian agro-industrial complex for the project period are projected to grow by 22%.

Conclusion. Digital technologies, including process automation, drones, and IoT devices, can significantly enhance the productivity and efficiency of agricultural enterprises.

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INTRODUCTION

The urgency of the digital transformation problem in agriculture stems from the fact that introduction of digital technologies enables optimized production processes, cost reduction, and product quality improvement. Digital technologies such as precision farming and weather monitoring systems would allow farmers to adapt to climate change, optimize resource utilization, and mitigate risks associated with crop loss. Digital solutions contribute to a more rational use of natural resources, reducing the negative impact on the environment and the development of environmentally sustainable agricultural models.

Automation and robotization of production help compensate for the shortage of qualified workers in rural areas, which is an urgent problem for many regions of Russia. Digital transformation enables Russian agricultural producers to integrate into global value chains, gain access to new sales markets, and enhance the industry's export potential.

In recent decades, the global demand for food skyrocketed due to the rapid increase in population. Along with this, due to the rise in real income and the development of people's consciousness, the demand for higher-quality products and calories increases. People are increasingly opting for healthier and more natural products; thus, in developed countries, a consumer basket of organic products gradually forms. In this regard, the increasing share of organic products in the market is noteworthy. Therefore, farmers are faced with the task of not only increasing the yield of food crops and the productivity of agricultural animals but also increasing the usefulness of their products [1; 2].

Due to the limited land resources as the main factor of production, the peculiarity of regional climatic conditions, and the increase in extreme meteorological phenomena, farmers face conflicts of goals in the event of an increase in productivity and agricultural production. That is, soil erosion occurs everywhere, as do pollution of water bodies due to the application of fertilizers or plant protection products, and emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere. Due to its multifaceted applications, digital transformation provides a basis for sustainable development, enabling a simultaneous increase in productivity and efficiency during production. At the same time, based on the receipt, collection, and processing of information, it becomes possible to optimize processes in the field of product processing [3].

Digitalization of production processes cannot be considered an end in itself; it should be viewed as a factor in increasing productivity and production efficiency in general, including in agricultural production. In the face of growing competition, the use of innovative digital technologies is becoming increasingly important as it provides more opportunities to increase the productivity of production processes and product quality, resulting in enhanced economic efficiency, which enables these organizations to gain a competitive advantage. Since the use of digital technologies, more products are created with the best quality characteristics at a relatively low cost. The noted diversity in the scope of digital technologies requires the development of specific decisions from the relevant ministries and departments regarding particular areas of its application. On the part of state bodies, standards and standards for their application should be developed. Moreover, the state should provide centralized services and some incentive measures for the use of digital technologies, as is done in developed countries. To implement these measures, they utilize concessional lending, preferential taxes, subsidies, and other economic levers for enterprises and organizations that willingly adopt modern innovative technologies and create new innovative infrastructures and jobs to offset them [4].

The paper aims to analyze the state of digitalization of agricultural production and identify reserves for its improvement in Russia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material of the article was research and analytical reports on digital transformation in agriculture, published in scientific journals and reports of international and Russian organizations: "Environment, Development and Sustainability"; "Precision Agriculture"; "Environmental Science and Pollution Research"; "Environment, Development and Sustainability"; "Innovation, Technology, and Knowledge Management"; "Smart Innovation"; "Systems and Technologies", etc.

The studies were carried out based on data from statistical reporting of the Russian Federation, its constituent entities, and the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation over the past decade, as well as on the materials of the federal target program for the digitalization of agriculture when collecting and processing data, abstract-logical, monographic, computational-constructive, comparative analyzes and statistical methods were used.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. V. Nemchenko et al. write that the digital transformation of agricultural production is defined as a universal response to existing challenges and threats to agriculture [5].

A. I. Solodovnik et al. consider directions and trends in the development of the digital economy and agriculture 4.0. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of digital agroecosystems, as they have not been sufficiently studied [6].

It has been empirically proven that the digital transformation of agriculture can increase farmers' incomes by increasing production efficiency, expanding sales channels, and promoting the modernization of the agricultural structure [7].

S. G. Cheglakova et al. identify potential applications of digital technologies in agricultural enterprises and objective factors that limit their use in the industry. The authors substantiate the need to assess the likelihood of bankruptcy when evaluating the potential benefits of introducing digital technologies in agricultural organizations [8].

Today, many researchers are actively exploring the applications of digital technologies in agriculture, with particular focus on the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, machine learning, and blockchain.

R. D. H. Lumbantobing et al. write that IoT, blockchain, and data mining play an essential role in implementing digital transformation in agricultural supply chains [9].

R. Falcão et al. explore the possibilities and limitations of using digital twins in the agricultural field [10].

C. Ganeshkumar & A. David write that remote sensing systems, artificial intelligence, immersive reality, the Internet of Things, and blockchain create new opportunities for food businesses in a digital-based agri-food system. The authors believe that digitalization plays a vital role in intelligent and precision farming. Additionally, most farmers are studying digital technologies in agriculture [11].

A. Gabriel & M. Gandorfer focus on the introduction of precision farming and other digital technologies, as well as the use of several technologies in the small agricultural region in southern Germany. The authors note the already traditional use of technologies, such as automatic milking systems, digital field recordings, and automatic steering systems, which increases the need to introduce additional technologies [12].

F. Büyükakin & O. B. Soylu assess the possibilities of integrating virtual and augmented reality into the agricultural production process [13].

S. Sridhar et al. consider the use of digital tools in the agri-food sector a promising approach for developing a self-sufficient society [14].

M. S. Kyzurov et al. justify that the transition from digital agriculture to agriculture 4.0 is the most promising scenario for ensuring food security of the future economy [15].

Z. Fu et al. write that coordination of agricultural production and the environment is an essential aspect of sustainable growth. At the same time, digital transformation provides new technical means to achieve this goal [16].

Digital transformation significantly enhances innovation in green technologies, scales up agricultural activities, and optimizes the structure of agrarian cultivation, thereby contributing to green growth [17]. Digital technological innovation is essential to promoting low-carbon development in agriculture [18]. To achieve regional balanced low-carbon development in agriculture, it is necessary to encourage the transfer of developed technologies from high-level regions to low-level regions [19].

V. I. Trukhachev examines the latest research on digital transformations occurring in agriculture worldwide, with a particular focus on Russia and the member countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States. The authors note that topics such as intelligent systems, data analytics and machine learning, digital platforms, services, and ecosystems, as well as the Internet of Things, are widely covered in the scientific literature [20].

A. G. Ibragimov et al. consider the problem of digitalization of the global and Russian economies, as well as the impact of the main trends in its development on the personnel of the agro-industrial complex. The authors conclude that it is essential for the digitalization of the economy to have appropriate human resources, in particular IT specialists [21].

T. I. Gulyaeva et al. clarify the concept of "development of personnel potential" and its features in the context of the development of information and communication technologies, automation of production, and the expansion of digital platform use. The authors conclude that the main directions of digitalization in the agricultural sector of the economy objectively require the advanced development of human resources, and as a result, the modernization and restructuring of agricultural education to increase the demand for graduates of agricultural universities in the new economic conditions [22].

P. G. Asalkhanov is researching the state of digitalization in agriculture in the Irkutsk region, proposing measures to stimulate the use of modern technologies in the area's agro-industrial complex. The authors also emphasize the need to train highly qualified specialists in the field of digital transformation, as well as to establish a register of product manufacturers with the necessary resources and capabilities to utilize digital agricultural technologies [23].

O. G. Karataeva et al. analyze the prospects for the digital transformation of agricultural production in the Chuvash Republic. The authors write that the introduction of digital technologies and the use of online platforms will revive traditional outputs for each region (for example, hops, flax, and technical hemp) and agriculture [24].

Thus, it is essential to examine the existing theories and models of digital transformation in agriculture, as well as their adaptation to the specific conditions of Russia. Based on an analysis of existing theories and data, it is necessary to develop new approaches and models that describe the process of digital transformation in Russian agriculture. To understand the features of digital transformation in agriculture in Russia, it is necessary to conduct empirical research, collect and analyze data on the introduction of digital technologies, their effectiveness, and impact on productivity.

RESULTS

The World Bank's 2020 report On Global Development indicates a low level of digital technology use in Russia. It is noted that Russia ranks 41st in the international ranking in terms of readiness for the digital economy. The list is headed by Singapore, followed by Finland, Sweden, Norway, the USA, the Netherlands, Switzerland, England, Luxembourg, and Japan, among others. According to the economic results obtained from the use of innovative technologies, Russia ranks 38th. Here, too, the list is headed by the abovementioned countries [25].

Russia's significant lag behind developed countries is associated with the imperfection of its regulatory framework for digital technology use and an unfavorable business environment, resulting in the inferior use of digital technologies in business structures.

According to leading scientists, economists, and agricultural specialists, the use of modern digital technologies enhances the energy efficiency of labor in the industry,

resulting in increased labor productivity. As a result, the cost of production decreases and the profitability of production increases. The low level of digitalization of technological processes in Russia also resulted in a low energy burden for agricultural organizations. Since advanced countries are 3.7-6.0 times more energy-intensive in agricultural labor than Russia (see Fig. 1) [26].

Figure 1 Energy intensity of labor in agricultural organizations (energy capacity in hp per 100 hectares of sown area)

Summarizing all the above, we can say that the use of digital technologies provides countries with a significant advantage in competitiveness. In the modern world, digitalization is seen as the driving force of the economy. Given this trend, the Government of the Russian Federation, starting in 2017, began to attach particular importance to the digitalization of the economy in all areas of its activities. Realizing the seriousness of the problem, the Government of the Russian Federation developed and, on December 24, 2018, launched the national project "Digital Economy of the Russian Federation" for 2018-2024, with the budget of 1634.9 billion rubles. The project outlines the main areas of activity for which specific measures include:

1. collection, storage, and processing of information;
2. monitoring and application software for animal husbandry and crop production;
3. optimization of the in-process;
4. creation of highly targeted information platforms;
5. creation of standard data processing and transmission systems between interconnected ministries and departments;
6. digital market analysis systems;

7. organization of digital forms of training, advanced training, retraining, and consulting of specialists;
8. creation of an efficient data infrastructure
9. state support for Russian research and development.

As part of the Russian Federation's Digital Economy program, Russia plans to bring the Internet to remote areas of the country, store government documents in cloud storage, and provide 80% of government services in digital form by 2025.

Taking into account the peculiarities of agricultural production, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation in 2019 developed a project "Digital Agriculture" for 2019-2024, with the budget of 300 billion rubles, including 152 billion rubles from the federal budget of the Russian Federation, 8 billion rubles from the budgets of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, and 140 billion rubles from extrabudgetary sources. The main objectives of the Digital Agriculture Project are:

1. compared to 2018, by 2024, the productivity of agricultural enterprises is expected to increase by 2 times.
2. identifying and analyzing point problems and conditions that restrain the development of the agro-industrial complex, to increase measures of state support in terms of stimulating the digitalization of the economy of the agro-industrial complex;
3. to promptly transfer data on agricultural lands and ensure their subsequent accounting, monitoring, and analysis, and organize interdepartmental interaction of federal executive bodies in the digital platform "Digital Agriculture";
4. to conduct a phased regulation of the implementation of the departmental project "Digital Agriculture" in Russia;
5. to form a system for training specialists for agricultural enterprises with high digital literacy.

According to the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation, digital technologies in the agro-industrial complex, combined with point optimization of technological processes and associated costs, will increase profitability in agricultural production by approximately 23% [27].

The main arguments in support of the digitalization of agricultural production are the need to fulfill the following problematic tasks associated with Russia's lag behind the advanced countries of the world:

1. to improve the quantity and quality of agricultural products;
2. to optimize capital investments in agricultural production;

3. to increase the energy-bearing capacity of labor in agriculture;
4. to reduce labour intensity and increase agricultural production productivity;
5. to reduce the harmful environmental impact of agricultural production;
6. to reduce dependence of agriculture on human, natural, and climatic factors.

Among all the listed advantages of innovative digital technologies in agriculture, one of particular interest is their impact on the yield of food crops and the productivity of farm animals. As evidenced by the data in Table 1 and Figure 2, Russia lags 2-3 times behind the advanced countries (where digital technologies are effectively used in crop production and animal husbandry) in food crops yield and 1.1-1.5 times in dairy cows productivity, (see Table 1 and Fig. 2) [28; 8; 2]

Table 1

Main food crops yield and cows productivity in the leading countries, including Russia, in the context of digital agriculture for 2021.

Food crops	Germany	France	China	USA	Netherlands	Great Britain	Russia
Wheat, kg/ha	75.3	68	58.1	86.9	83.2	74	27
Rice, c/ha	64.2	54.8	70.3	86.2	81.3	72.4	57.6
Corn per grain, kg/ha	79	7.2	62.9	111	88.3	84.3	50.8
Sugar beet, t/ha	76.2	83.9	59.7	73.4	77.8	66.1	47
Potatoes, t/ha	44.4	39	17	49	42	38.7	25.8
Vegetables, t/ha	38.5	34.5	25.8	50.2	44.5	37.5	17.0
Melons, t/ha	36.8	33.8	22.5	43.2	35.3	32.1	15.8
Milk yield per 1 cow, tons per year	8.2	7.2	8	10.5	9.1	8.1	6.9

Figure 2 Milk yield per 1 cow worldwide for 2021, tons per year

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Research prospects in this area are related to the fact that digital technologies, such as process automation, drones, and IoT devices, can significantly increase the productivity and efficiency of agricultural enterprises [30].

The benefits of digital solutions include a more efficient use of resources such as water, fertilizers, and fuel, which helps reduce costs and minimize environmental impact. Moreover, digital tools allow:

- adapting the methods of tillage and crop care to specific conditions;
- accurately monitoring the condition of crops, weather and other factors affecting the harvest;
- manufacturers, processors and distributors more efficiently interacting;
- creating new opportunities for the development of the agricultural technology market, including new products and services.

The transition to digital agriculture necessitates the training of qualified specialists, which in turn contributes to the creation of new jobs and the development of relevant skills among the population [31]. At the same time, government support and investment in digital technologies for agriculture can accelerate the transformation process and provide the necessary resources for innovation [32].

Here, we agree with V. Babenko et al., who write that to increase the efficiency, productivity, and sustainability of digital agriculture, it is necessary to bridge the digital divide, promote cooperation, ensure data privacy and security, support small farms, and encourage innovation [33].

In all spheres of economic activity, especially in agriculture, the use of innovative digital technologies lags significantly behind that of competing countries in Europe, Asia, and other continents. Realizing the seriousness of the problem, the Government of the Russian Federation adopted the National Project “Digital Economy of the Russian Federation” (in 2018) and the program “Digital Agriculture” (in 2019). Under these two programs, the total budget financing amount is 1,934.9 billion rubles. Due to such budget financing, by 2025, agricultural production is expected to grow by 16.3%, and agricultural exports are projected to reach \$45 billion, representing a 20% increase from 2017. Under these programs, investment in the Russian Federation’s agro-industrial complex is expected to increase by 22% by 2025.

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